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Method development and validation for determination of thiosultap sodium, thiocyclam and nereistoxin in pepper matrix.

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Abstract

This work reports a method for extraction and analysis of thiosultap sodium, thiocyclam and nereistoxin in pepper. Different extraction methods were tested to attain the best recoveries. The final extraction method combines acetonitrile extraction in an acidic medium with ultrasonic extraction followed by a cleanup step with anhydrous MgSO_4 . The analyses were performed on a Linear Ion Trap Quadrupole LC-MS/MS in negative mode for thiosultap sodium and in positive mode for thiocyclam and nereistoxin. Recovery studies carried out on peppers spiked at different fortification levels (20 and 200 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) yielded average recoveries in the range 58-87 % with RSD (%) values below 20 %. Calibration curves covering two orders of magnitude were performed and they were linear over the concentration range studied (0.001 to 0.5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$). Instrumental detection limits (LOD) were in the low $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ range. Stability studies of thiosultap sodium in water were accomplished evaluating a 100 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ solution of this compound in water. It was analyzed during seven days, after which a degradation of more than 80% of thiosultap sodium could be observed.

Introduction

Constant positive findings of non-authorized pesticides in the European Union have brought out the need of including some of these low-frequency pesticides into the routine analysis. Thiosultap sodium and thiocyclam are two of these low-frequency compounds. They are known as nereistoxin analogues. Nereistoxin is a naturally occurring insecticide isolated from the marine segmented worms, *Lumbriconereis heteropoda* [1]. Its structure was elucidated by Okaichi and Hashimoto in 1962 [2]. A variety of nereistoxin derivatives have been known for decades, including thiosultap sodium, thiocyclam, cartap and bensultap. Of the many analogs synthesized only those that are metabolized back to the original nereistoxin after application are active. In this sense, members of this class are proinsecticides, meaning that they are applied in their manufactured form but are known to degrade to a specific active component. [1, 3-5]. Both thiosultap sodium and thiocyclam are not included in the directive 91/414/EEC [6], therefore, no maximum residue limit (MRL) is established for them under the Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 [7, 8], and so a default MRL of 0.01 mg kg⁻¹, according to Art 18(1)(b) Reg. 396/2005, is applied to these insecticides. Despite these restrictions in the EU, thiosultap sodium and nereistoxin are extensively used as pesticides in vegetables, rice, potatoes and fruit trees in other countries that are exporting their products to Europe. At the beginning of the last year, nereistoxin was found in a tomato sample coming from Turkey, as indicates the pesticide residue finding in the *Pesticides Online* database [9]. There is little literature about experimental methodology for their analysis. Traditional methods for analysis of nereistoxin analogues were based on the conversion of the parent compound to nereistoxin, which was then measured by gas chromatography. Chuan-Jiang Tao *et al.* [10] reported a method for the determination of monosultap, the monosodium form of thiosultap sodium, in tomato and soil by conversion into nereistoxin with alkaline hydrolysis and further analysis by gas chromatography with flame photometric detection and confirmation with GC-MS, which

implied laborious and time consuming extraction, derivatization and cleaning up procedures. Nereistoxin and some of its metabolites have been analyzed in human serum using headspace solid-phase microextraction and GC-MS [5], and also HPLC with electrochemical detection [11]. Several publications have reported analysis of thiocyclam in vegetables. Kmellár *et al.* [12] developed an LC-MS/MS method in multi-class vegetables after QuEChERS extraction. A similar approach also using LC-MS/MS, but with ethyl acetate extraction was the one of Mol *et al.* [13]. Thiocyclam has also been analyzed in olive oil by LC-MS/MS after QuEChERS extraction for high oil content commodities [14]. The main objective of this work was to develop a simple and sensitive method for the determination of thiosultap sodium, thiocyclam and nereistoxin in peppers, using a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer. Identification and confirmation of target compounds by electrospray tandem mass spectrometry was based on two MS/MS transitions (selected reaction monitoring (SRM) mode). The pesticides were extracted from the vegetable matrix using a liquid–liquid partitioning step with acetonitrile in an acidic medium with ultrasonic extraction followed by a dispersive solid-phase extraction (DSPE) clean-up step with anhydrous MgSO₄. A validation of the method, in terms of recoveries, sensitivity, linearity and precision, was also performed.

Experimental

Chemical and reagents

(a) Standards

Pesticide analytical standards of high purity (> 90 %) of thiosultap sodium (Disodium S,S'-[2-(dimethylamino)trimethylene]di(thiosulfate)), thiocyclam hydrogenoxalate (N,N-Dimethyl-1,2,3-trithian-5-yl amine hydrogen oxalate) and nereistoxin oxalate (N,N-Dimethyl-1,2-dithiolan-4-amine oxalate) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Ausburg, Germany). Chemical structures of the studied pesticides are shown in Fig. 1. Individual pesticide stock

solutions of thiosultap sodium, thiocyclam and nereistoxin ($1000 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$) were prepared in acetonitrile and stored at -20°C .

(b) Solvents

HPLC-grade acetonitrile and methanol were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). A Milli-Q-Plus ultra-pure water system from Millipore (Milford, MA, USA) was used throughout the study to obtain the HPLC-grade water used during the analyses. Glacial Acetic acid was obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Chlorhidric acid was acquired from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Pesticide-grade ethyl acetate was purchased from J.T. Baker (Deventer, Netherlands).

(c) Reagents

Anhydrous magnesium sulphate was from Sigma–Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). PSA (primary-secondary amine) Bond Elut was obtained from Varian, Inc. (Palo Alto, CA, USA). Sodium chloride was acquired from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Trihydrated Sodium acetate was from Riedel-de Haën (Seelze, Germany).

Sample preparation

Pepper was selected as a representative matrix of the *water content* group. Red peppers were acquired in the local market and were homogeneously blended with a SK-3 Sammic (Azpeitia, Spain) chopper and stored at 4°C before spiking and sample extraction. A previous analysis of the sample was performed in order to ensure that it did not contain any of the studied compounds, and this sample was selected as blank for spiking, calibration curves, and recovery purposes.

Spiking procedure

The fact that nereistoxin analogues degrade into nereistoxin has been studied by many authors [3-5, 15] and for this reason the recovery tests were performed individually for each compound. Thus, three batches of recoveries were made following the next procedure: a representative 200 g portion of homogenised pepper was weighed and transferred to a glass mortar. Then, aliquots of the individual standard solutions of thiosultap sodium, thiocyclam or nereistoxin were added. In order to assess the homogeneity of the sample, the mixture was blended in the mortar for 30 minutes. Then the sample was allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 hour until analysis. The final spiking concentration levels were of 20 and 200 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in the pepper samples.

Extraction procedure

The employed procedure was a modification of the original QuEChERS method [16]. The extraction method comprised the following steps: a representative 15 g portion of previously homogenized sample was weighted in a 50 ml PTFE centrifugation tube. Then 3 ml of chlorhydric acid 2 N were added and the tube was vigorously shaken by hand for 2 minutes. Afterwards, 12 ml of acetonitrile with 1% acetic acid (v/v) were added into each tube using a solvent dispenser. After that, 6 g of anhydrous magnesium sulphate and 2.5 g of trihydrated sodium acetate were added, and the tube was shaken again by hand during 4 minutes. Then it was placed in an ultrasonic bath for 4 minutes, and finally it was centrifuged at 3700 rpm for 4 minutes. For the cleanup step, a 5 ml aliquot of the extract (upper layer) was taken with a pipette and transferred to a 15 ml PTFE centrifugation tube containing 750 mg of anhydrous magnesium sulphate. This tube was then shaken for 20 seconds using a vortex mixer and then it was centrifuged again for 4 minutes at 3700 rpm. Finally, 1 ml of the final extract, containing 1 g of sample per ml, was evaporated under a gentle stream of nitrogen until near dryness, and

then it was reconstituted with acetonitrile/water (30/70, v/v). The obtained extract was then filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE filter (Millex FG, Millipore, Milford, USA) before analysis.

LC-MS/MS Analysis

For the LC analysis, an Agilent 1100 HPLC system with a binary pump was used. The analytical column employed was a reversed-phase C8 of 150 mm \times 4.6 mm and 5 μm particle size (Agilent Zorbax Eclipse XDB). The mobile phases were acetonitrile and Milli-Q water. The gradient program started with 30 % of acetonitrile that stayed 2 minutes in isocratic mode and then it increased linearly up to 100 % in 8 minutes, and then remained constant for 5 minutes. After this 15 minutes run time, 10 minutes of post-time followed using the initial 30 % of acetonitrile for the conditioning of the column. The flow rate was constant, 0.4 ml \cdot min $^{-1}$, during the whole process and 20 μl of sample were injected in every case.

For the mass spectrometric analysis a hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap (QqQLIT) in MRM mode was used. It was a 3200 QTRAPTM MS/MS analyzer (Applied Biosystem, Concord, Ontario, Canada) equipped with an electrospray source operating in both positive and negative ionization modes (positive for nereistoxin and thiocyclam and negative for thiosultap sodium). The optimization of the instrumental parameters for each compound was performed by flow injection analysis (FIA), injecting individual standard solutions directly into the source. The main parameters were set as follows: *Positive mode*: Curtain Gas: 10 psi; Nebulizer Gas: 50 psi; Auxiliary Gas: 50 psi; Source Temperature: 500 $^{\circ}$ C; Ion Spray Voltage: 5000 V. *Negative mode*: Curtain Gas: 10 psi; Nebulizer Gas: 50 psi; Auxiliary Gas: 50 psi; Source Temperature: 500 $^{\circ}$ C; Ion Spray Voltage: 3500 V. Nitrogen was used as the nebulizer and the collision gas. Table 1 shows the values of the instrumental settings optimized for each compound: declustering and entrance potential for precursor ions and collision energy for product ions. The acquisition was performed in two experiments in the same run, one in

negative mode and the other one in positive mode. As only two and four transitions respectively were scanned in each mode, a dwell time of 200 ms was used. For confirmation of the studied pesticides two selected reaction monitoring (SRM) transitions and a correct ratio between the abundances of the two optimized SRM transitions (SRM2/SRM1) were used, along with retention time matching. For quantification, the most intense SRM transition was selected. Applied Biosystems/MDS SCIEX Analyst software was used for data acquisition and processing

Validation Study

Once the extraction method was developed, a validation study of the whole process was performed. Quantification of the pesticides in the spiked samples was carried out comparing the peak areas of the samples with those of matrix matched standard solutions. These, as well as the matrix-matched calibration curves were constructed by evaporating a known volume of blank pepper extract under a gentle stream of nitrogen and reconstituting it with the same volume of a standard solution of the desired concentration. The limit of detection (LOD) of each compound was determined as the minimum concentration of analyte that generated a signal to noise ratio (S/N) of 3. This parameter was evaluated in the confirmation transition (SRM2). For the limits of quantification (LOQs) the criterion was the minimum concentration of analyte that gave a S/N ratio of 10. This was studied in the quantification transition (SRM1). In order to verify them empirically, matrix-matched standards solutions of those theoretical concentrations were injected. Linearity was evaluated both in solvent and matrix (red pepper), using matrix-matched calibration curves prepared as described before, in a concentration range of 0.001 - 0.5 mg·kg⁻¹. The matrix effect was studied by comparison of the slopes of the calibration curves in solvent and in matrix. The precision of the method was estimated by determining the inter- and intra-day relative standard deviation (RSD, %) by the repeated

analysis (n=5) of a spiked pepper extract at a 0.1 mg kg⁻¹ level, from run-to-run over one day and five days, respectively.

Results and discussion

Optimization of LC-MS/MS parameters

The optimization of the compounds was made by flow injection analysis (FIA) of the individual standard solutions at a concentration of 1 mg·kg⁻¹ in acetonitrile/water (50/50, v/v). In this process the precursor and the product ions were chosen, along with the optimum declustering and entrance potentials for the precursor ion and the collision energies for the product ions. The transitions of the most abundant product ions (SRM1) were used for quantification and the second ones in abundance (SRM2), for confirmation.

The first step involved selecting the precursor ion for each compound. For thiocyclam and nereistoxin the protonated molecule [M+H]⁺ was the most abundant, and so it was chosen as the precursor ion. For thiosultap sodium, as it worked in negative mode, it was the deprotonated [M-H]⁻ molecule the most abundant, after losing the two sodium atoms that formed the salt. Some fragment ions were observed for all the compounds, but at low intensity, so they were not taken into account. Then, the optimum declustering and entrance potentials were chosen for the precursor ions. The declustering potential controls the potential difference between the orifice plate and the first quadrupole. It is used to minimize solvent cluster ions, which may attach to the sample. If the declustering potential is too high, the sample ion itself may fragment. The entrance potential guides and focuses the ions through the high pressure region, so the optimum one will permit the maximum number of ions to go into the collision cell, and so, the best sensitivity will be achieved. The selected conditions are shown in Table 1.

Afterwards, in the *Product Ion* mode, two product ions for each compound were selected, along with their corresponding optimum collision energies. The collision energy is the amount of

energy that the precursor ions receive as they are accelerated into the collision cell, where they collide with gas molecules and fragment. Thiocyclam (m/z 73.0) and nereistoxin (m/z 61.1) yielded low mass ions. Obtaining such low masses represents a disadvantage as it entails a decrease in specificity. Nevertheless these ions were chosen for product ions as no other higher mass ions were sensitive enough. The tentative molecular formulas of the selected fragments are shown in Table 1.

Optimization of the extraction procedure

The most employed extraction method for fruits and vegetables by the European laboratories is the QuEChERS method. For this reason, this one was the one we started from. Some modifications of this method have been developed, but for the first approach we used the original QuEChERS method. It consisted on weighing 10 g of previously homogenized and spiked sample into a 50 ml PTFE centrifugation tube. Then, 10 ml of acetonitrile were added using a solvent dispenser, and the sample was shaken vigorously by hand during 1 minute. After that, 4 g anhydrous $MgSO_4$ and 1 g NaCl were added and the tube was again shaken by hand for another minute. Then it was centrifuged at 3700 rpm for 4 minutes.

For the cleanup step, a 5 ml aliquot of the extract (upper layer) was taken with a pipette and transferred to a 15 ml PTFE centrifugation tube containing 750 mg of anhydrous $MgSO_4$ and 125 mg PSA. This tube was then shaken for 30 seconds using a vortex mixer and then it was centrifuged again for 4 minutes at 3700 rpm. Finally, 1 ml of the final extract was evaporated under a gentle stream of nitrogen until near dryness, and then it was reconstituted with acetonitrile/water (30/70, v/v). The obtained extract was then filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE filter before analysis. The recoveries obtained with this method were not acceptable, especially for thiosultap sodium, as the average recovery was of 23 %. In an attempt to increase the recoveries, we tried the buffered QueChERS method [17], which employs sodium acetate and

acetic acid to buffer the extract and so improve the results for certain pesticides that are not stable at basic pH, which is the case of the studied compounds. This method consists on weighing a representative 15 g portion of previously homogenized sample in a 50 ml PTFE centrifugation tube. Then 15 ml of acetonitrile with 1 % acetic acid (v/v) were added, along with 6 g of anhydrous magnesium sulphate and 1.5 g of sodium acetate. The tube was shaken by hand during 4 minutes and it was centrifuged at 3700 rpm for another 4 minutes. For the cleanup step, a 5 ml aliquot of the extract (upper layer) was taken with a pipette and transferred to a 15 ml PTFE centrifugation tube containing 750 mg of anhydrous magnesium sulphate and 250 mg of PSA. This tube was then shaken for 30 seconds using a vortex mixer and then it was centrifuged again for 4 minutes at 3700 rpm. Finally, 1 ml of the final extract was evaporated under a gentle stream of nitrogen until near dryness, and then it was reconstituted with acetonitrile/water (30/70, v/v). The obtained extract was filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE filter. Once again the recovery results obtained with this method were not good for any of the studied compounds. It has been reported that pesticides with acidic groups interact with aminosorbents such as PSA [18]. As thiosultap sodium has acidic properties, we decided to avoid the use of PSA for the extraction. The results were slightly better, so we resolved to follow in this direction. Based on the pesticides structures we thought it could be positive to perform the extraction in an acidic medium, in order to enable the protonated form of these molecules. We tried adding 3 ml of chlorhydric acid 5N and 2N at the beginning of the extraction, resulting that the recoveries increased when using HCl 2 N. In order to improve the recoveries, we added a sonication step after shaking by hand, and found that this procedure raised the recoveries to an acceptable level. The final extraction method is described in the experimental section under *Extraction procedure*. The results of this extraction method are shown in Table 2.

Validation of the method in peppers

In order to prove the effectiveness of the developed method, we carried out its validation. For this purpose, we chose pepper as a representative matrix of the *high water content* group of matrices [19]. Signal suppression or enhancement as a result of matrix effect can severely compromise quantitative analysis of the pesticides at trace levels, as well as it can greatly affect the method reproducibility and accuracy. For this reason, matrix effect was evaluated during the validation of the method. This, as well as linearity were investigated using solvent and matrix-matched calibration curves at six concentration levels covering two orders of magnitude: from 0.001 - 0.5 mg·kg⁻¹. The calibration curves of the selected insecticides are plotted in Fig. 2. Table 3 shows the calibration equations obtained for the pesticides in pepper matrix and their correlation coefficients. As it can be observed, the linearity of the analytical response within the studied range of two orders of magnitude is good, with correlation coefficients higher than 0.99 in all cases. The matrix effect was studied by comparison of the slopes of the calibration curves in solvent and in matrix. In Table 3 the ratio between both slopes and the percentage of signal enhancement or suppression are shown. If the slope is 1 it means there is no matrix effect, but if it is less than 1 it implies that signal suppression is taking place, and if it is higher than one it means there is signal enhancement. The matrix effect is also presented as a percentage of the difference between the slopes of the corresponding calibration curves and the degree of enhancement or suppression in the signal response. In this case, for the three studied pesticides, strong signal suppression takes place in pepper matrix, as it is of 53% for thiosultap sodium, 51% for thiocyclam and 48% for nereistoxin. This fact highlights the importance of performing quantification with matrix matched calibration curves. For this reason, the calibration and quantification was carried out using matrix matched standards. The LODs and LOQs are also presented in Table 3. These were estimated from the injection of matrix-matched standard solutions at concentration levels corresponding to a S/N of 3 and 10,

respectively. The LOD was determined in the confirmation transition (SRM2) and the LOQ in the quantification transition (SRM1). In all the cases they are far below the 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ level established for non authorised compounds, as the LOQs are of 5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for thiosultap sodium, 1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for thiocyclam and 0.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for nereistoxin in pepper matrix. The intra- and inter-day RSDs were studied in order to evaluate the precision of the developed method. The RSD ($n = 5$) values for run-to-run studies were in the range 1.5-8.1 % and the inter-day RSD ($n = 5$) values were between 3.4 and 9.9 %, as can be seen in Table 3. These demonstrate the precision of the method and so, its effectiveness for quantitative purposes. As an example, SRM1 of the three insecticides studied corresponding to the analysis of a spiked pepper sample fortified with 0.02 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ is shown in Fig. 3.

Due to the complex nature of the pepper matrix, another criterion we used for identification of the pesticides was the SRM ratio, calculated as the quotient between SRM2 and SRM1. Recommended maximum permitted tolerances for relative ion intensities are given in the SANCO analytical quality control procedures for pesticide residue analysis [19]. The tolerance range indicated in these guidelines for LC–MS techniques is from 20 to 50 %. In order to validate this SRM ratio in matrix we calculated them for pesticide standard solutions in solvent and in pepper matrix. Table 4 summarizes the SRM ratios, corresponding to the average values obtained for a range of concentration from LOQ up to 500 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. Also included in the table are the coefficients of variation (CVs, %) of the SRM ratio within this range of concentrations (expressed in percentage) and the difference between the SRM ratios in solvent and matrix. The CVs obtained for the pesticides studied indicate optimal system performance. This means that variations observed when comparing SRM ratios at low and high concentrations of pesticide standard, as well as the responses in matrix and solvent, were within an acceptable confidence interval. For all of the pesticides, the differences between the SRM ratios in solvent and matrix, within the range of concentrations evaluated, were lower than 8 %. Based on these results, it

can be deduced that the SRM ratio parameter can be used as a key criterion for identification and also for further quantitative analysis.

Stability of thiosultap sodium and thiocyclam

Due to the fact that thiosultap sodium and thiocyclam are proinsecticides, under certain circumstances it is known that they degrade into nereistoxin [3-5, 15]. In order to check the stability of the standard solutions of these compounds, stability studies of thiosultap sodium and thiocyclam in water were performed. Individual standard solutions of the studied compounds of $100 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ were prepared in water and analyzed during seven days. After this period of time, a degradation of more than 80 % of thiosultap sodium and 50 % of thiocyclam could be observed, showing degradation into nereistoxin. Fig. 4 shows the stability graph of thiosultap sodium and thiocyclam during seven days.

Conclusions

A new method for the extraction and analysis of thiosultap sodium, thiocyclam and nereistoxin in pepper was developed by means of LC-MS/MS techniques, working in both positive and negative mode. Extraction of the samples involved dispersive solid-phase extraction in acidic medium and sonication. Validation of the method was carried out following EU guidelines. Stability studies of thiosultap sodium and thiocyclam in water were performed during seven days, after which a degradation of more than 50% for both compounds could be observed.

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References

- [1] Lee SJ, Tomizawa M, Casida JE (2003) *J Agric Food Chem* 51: 2646-2652
- [2] Okaichi T, Hashimoto Y, (1962) *Agr Biol Chem* 26: 224-227
- [3] Lee S, Caboni P, Tomizawa M, Casida JE (2004) *J Agric Food Chem* 52: 95-98
- [4] Ware G, Whitacre D (2004) *The pesticide Book*. Meister Media Worldwide
- [5] Namera A, Watanabe T, Yashiki M, Kojima T, Urabe T (1999) *J Chrom Sci* 37: 77-82
- [6] Council Directive 91/414/EEC of 15 July 1991 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market
- [7] Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC with EEA relevance
- [8] http://ec.europa.eu/sanco_pesticides/public/index.cfm
- [9] Pesticide online database [www.pesticides-online.com].
- [10] Tao C J, Hu J Y, Li J Z (2007) *Can J Anal Sci and Spec* 52: 295-304
- [11] Fisher DH, Xie Y, Loring R (1993) *Anal Lett* 26: 1051 - 1063
- [12] Kmellár B, Fodor P, Pareja L, Ferrer C, Martínez-Uroz MA, Valverde A, Fernandez-Alba AR (2008) *J Chromatogr A* 1215:37–50

- [13] Mol HGJ, Rooseboom A, van Dam R, Roding M, Arondeus K, Sunarto S, (2007) *Anal Bioanal Chem* 389: 1715–1754
- [14] Hernando M D, Ferrer C, Ulaszewska M, García-Reyes JF, Molina-Díaz A, Fernández-Alba AR, (2007), *Anal Bioanal Chem*, 389:1815–1831
- [15] Lee S, Tomizawa M, Casida JE, (2003) *J Agric Food Chem* 51: 2646-2652
- [16] Anastassiades M, Lehotay SJ, Štajnbaher D, Schenck FJ (2003) *J AOAC Int* 86: 412-431
- [17] Lehotay SJ, Mastovska K, Lightfield AR (2005) *J AOAC Int* 88: 615-629
- [18] Anastassiades M, Scherbaum E, Taşdelen B, Štajnbaher D (2007) In: Ohkawa H, Miyagawa H, Lee PW (ed) *Pesticide Chemistry: Crop Protection, Public Health, Environmental Safety*. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim.
- [19] Document No. SANCO 10684/2009. Method validation and quality control procedures for pesticide residue analysis in food and feed. http://www.crl-pesticides.eu/library/docs/allcrl/AqcGuidance_Sanco_2009_10684.pdf

Fig. 1 Structures of the studied insecticides

Thiocyclam

(Mw: 181)

Thiosultap sodium

(Mw: 355)

Nereistoxin

(Mw: 149)

Fig. 2 Comparison of the calibration curves obtained for thiosultap sodium, thiocyclam and nereistoxin using pepper matrix-matched standards and solvent-based standards.

Fig. 3 Quantification selected reaction monitoring (SRM1) of the three insecticides studied corresponding to the analysis of a spiked pepper sample fortified with 0.02 mg·kg⁻¹. a) Thiosultap sodium, b) Nereistoxin, c) Thiocyclam.

Fig. 4 Stability study of thiosultap sodium and thiocyclam in a milli-Q water solution (0.1 mg·l⁻¹).

Table 1.- Values of the instrumental settings optimized for each compound: precursor ions, declustering potential (DP), entrance potential (EP), product ions and their collision energies (CE).

	Retention time (min)	Precursor Ion (m/z)	DP (V)	EP (V)	SRM1 (m/z)	CE 1 (eV)	SRM2 (m/z)	CE 2 (eV)
Thiosultap sodium	4.1	309.9 [C ₅ H ₁₂ NO ₆ S ₄] ⁻	27	5	230.0 [C ₅ H ₁₂ NO ₃ S ₃] ⁻	13	184.9 [C ₃ H ₅ O ₃ S ₃] ⁻	18
Thiocyclam	4.2	182.0 [C ₅ H ₁₂ NS ₃] ⁺	32	4	137.1 [C ₃ H ₅ S ₃] ⁺	20	73.0 [C ₃ H ₅ S] ⁺	35
Nereistoxin	3.6	150.1 [C ₅ H ₁₂ NS ₂] ⁺	39	3	105.0 [C ₃ H ₅ S ₂] ⁺	20	61.1 [C ₂ H ₅ S] ⁺	35

Table 2 Results of the recovery study obtained at two spiking levels.

	Spiking level			
	20 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$		200 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	
	Mean Recovery ^a (%)	RSD ^b (%)	Mean Recovery ^a (%)	RSD ^b (%)
Thiosultap sodium	58.0	7.4	40.9	5.4
Thiocyclam	87.2	3.1	80.2	9.8
Nereistoxin	81.8	5.1	84.3	6.8

^a n=5 ^b Relative Standard Deviation (n=5)

Table 3.- Validation parameters obtained in pepper samples.

	Linearity equation in solvent	r^2	Linearity equation in matrix	r^2	Slope matrix/Slope solvent	Signal suppression (%)	Precision (RSD, %)		LOD ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
							Intra-day	Inter-day		
Thiosultap sodium	$y = 2538x - 8011$	0.9936	$y = 1191x - 2125$	0.9989	0.47	53	1.9	3.4	0.5	5.0
Thiocyclam	$y = 27339x + 349020$	0.9934	$y = 13442x - 44023$	0.9985	0.49	51	8.1	9.9	0.3	1.0
Nereistoxin	$y = 26186x + 167803$	0.9977	$y = 13606x + 84754$	0.9998	0.52	48	1.5	4.8	0.1	0.5

Table 4.- Average values of SRM ratio and their coefficients of variation (CVs, %) within a range of concentrations, in solvent and in pepper matrix, and percentages of difference between them.

	SRM ratio in solvent ^a	CV (%)	SRM ratio in matrix ^a	CV (%)	Difference between SRM ratios in solvent and in matrix (%)
Thiosultap sodium	0.65	2.6	0.64	3.9	1.5
Thiocyclam	0.34	8.0	0.33	4.4	2.9
Nereistoxin	0.26	8.7	0.24	9.8	7.7

^a Mean value from LOQ to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$